

A Clinical Evaluation of Efficacy of I-PRF for Papilla Reconstruction around Dental Implant and Natural Teeth

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Abstract- Background: The interdental papilla plays a vital role in aesthetics, and its loss results in gingival black triangles causing both aesthetic and functional issues. Conventional treatment methods have limited predictability, particularly around implants. Injectable platelet-rich fibrin (I-PRF) offers a promising minimally invasive approach for soft tissue regeneration.

Aim: To evaluate the efficacy of the i-PRF technique to augment deficient interproximal papilla around dental implants and between natural teeth.

Material and methods: This randomized comparative clinical trial included 36 sites from 25 patients aged 18–60 years with interdental and peri-implant black triangles. Patients were treated with injectable platelet-rich fibrin (i-PRF), and clinical parameters (PIS, BTH, BTW, BTA, and percentage fill) were recorded at baseline, 10 days, 1 month, and 3 months. **Result:** Group A showed statistically significant improvement in all clinical parameters, with better outcomes than Group B.

Conclusion: i-PRF is an effective minimally invasive technique for papilla reconstruction, with better results in interdental sites than peri-implant sites.

Keywords: i-PRF, Interdental Papilla, Peri- Implant Papilla

I.INTRODUCTION

The interdental papilla plays a crucial role in aesthetic dentistry, occupying the gingival embrasure and contributing significantly to smile appearance. Its loss leads to gingival black triangles (GBT) [1], causing aesthetic concerns along with functional issues such as food impaction and plaque accumulation. Due to its delicate structure and limited blood supply, papilla reconstruction remains challenging.

Various factors such as periodontal disease, trauma, and malocclusion contribute to papilla loss. Although multiple non-surgical and surgical techniques have been proposed, predictable outcomes are still limited, especially in cases with alveolar bone loss or around implants.

Platelet concentrates have shown promising results in tissue regeneration. Platelet-rich fibrin (PRF), introduced by **Choukroun et al.(2001)** [2], offers advantages over platelet-rich plasma (PRP), first described by **Kingsley (1954)** [3], due to its ease of use and lack of anticoagulants. Further advancements led to injectable PRF (I-PRF) in **2014** [4], which provides a higher concentration of growth factors.

Miron et al. (2017) [5] demonstrated that I-PRF enhances fibroblast migration and growth factor release, promoting soft tissue regeneration. Hence, I-PRF has emerged as a promising minimally invasive approach for interdental papilla reconstruction in both natural dentition and implant cases.

II. MATERIAL AND METHOD

This randomized comparative clinical trial was conducted in the Department of Periodontology, College of Dental Sciences and Research Centre, Manipal, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India, and included 36 sites from 25 patients (8 males, 17 females; aged 18–60 years) presenting with interdental and peri-implant black triangles. All patients received oral prophylaxis and oral hygiene instructions prior to treatment. Injectable platelet-rich fibrin (i-PRF) was administered into deficient papillae. Patients were divided into two groups: Group A (interdental papilla) and Group B (peri-implant papilla).

Inclusion criteria: Patients aged 18–60 years with good general health and fair oral hygiene, presenting with interdental papilla loss or peri-implant papilla deficiency with a detectable contact point, at least 20 natural teeth, and Papillary Index Score (PIS) of 1 or 2 (Jemt, 1997) [6] were included. **Exclusion criteria:** poor plaque control, active periodontal disease, systemic illness, immunocompromised status, absence of contact point, pregnancy or lactation, tobacco use, or those on medications affecting gingival status or coagulation were excluded.

Ethical clearance was obtained from the institutional ethical committee, and all participants were informed about the procedure. Written informed consent was obtained prior to the study. A detailed medical and dental history was recorded for all patients. All selected patients underwent oral prophylaxis and received oral hygiene instructions. Based on the treatment site, patients were divided into two groups: Group A (interdental papilla) and Group B (peri-implant papilla), both receiving injectable platelet-rich fibrin (i-PRF). i-PRF was prepared according to Miron RJ et al. (2017) [7]. Approximately 5 mL of intravenous blood was collected in plastic tubes without anticoagulant and centrifuged at 700 rpm for 3 minutes (60 g) at room temperature using a Remi R-4C centrifuge. The upper liquid layer (i-PRF) was immediately collected in an insulin syringe. Following administration of local anesthesia, i-PRF was injected using a one-point technique at a 45° angle, 2–3 mm apical to the papillary tip, with the bevel oriented upward. This was followed by gentle massage of the area for 1 minute. Patients were advised to avoid brushing and flossing in the treated area for 24 hours, after which brushing with a soft-bristled toothbrush was resumed.

Follow-up was done at 3-week intervals, and additional i-PRF injections were administered if required, up to a maximum of four applications. Clinical parameters were recorded at 10 days, 1 month, and 3 months. Standardized photographs were taken at each visit. Papillary Index Score (PIS) [6], Black Triangle Height (BTH), Width (BTW), Area (BTA), and percentage fill were evaluated and compared with baseline values.

Fig 1: Pre-operative at Baseline in interdental papilla

Fig 2: Injecting i-PRF

Fig 3: Pre-operative at Baseline Peri-implant papilla

Fig 4: Injecting i-PRF

Fig 5: i-PRF at 10 days in interdental papilla

Fig 6: i-PRF at 10 days in Peri-implant papilla

Fig 7: i-PRF at 1 month in interdental papilla

Fig 8: i-PRF at 1 month in Peri-implant papilla

Fig 9: i-PRF at 3 months in interdental papilla

Figure 10: i-PRF at 3 months in Peri-implant papilla

III. RESULT

Data obtained from the study were tabulated and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software (Version 22). Descriptive statistics were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation for all variables. Intragroup comparisons at baseline, 10 days, 1 month, and 3 months were performed using one-way repeated measures ANOVA. Intergroup comparisons were analyzed using the unpaired t-test. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant, with α error set at 5% and study power at 80% ($\beta = 20\%$). Group A included patients receiving injectable platelet-rich fibrin (i-PRF) in interdental papilla, while Group B included patients receiving i-PRF in peri-implant papilla.

TABLE 1
DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

Study Design	Total no. of sites	Gender		Age range (in years)	Total no. of groups	
Comparative	36	M	F	18 - 60 years	Group 1	Group 2
Clinical Study	(25 patients)	8	17		18 sites (11 patients)	18 sites (14 patients)

The demographic data of the study i.e., statistical data of males and females included in the study.

TABLE 2
INTERGROUP COMPARISON OF NUMBER OF APPLICATIONS

No. of Applications	Group A	Percentage	Group B	Percentage
1	4	22.2%	0	0%
2	14	77.8%	2	11.1%
3	0	0%	6	33.3%
4	0	0%	10	55.6%

This Table shows the percentage of intergroup comparison of the number of applications, of the data included in the study.

TABLE 3
INTERGROUP COMPARISON OF PAPILLARY INDEX SCORES (PIS)

Time Interval	Group A	Group B	Mean Difference	p-value
Baseline	1.06 ± 0.24	1.06 ± 0.24	0	1
10 Days	1.39 ± 0.50	1.06 ± 0.24	0.33	0.02*
1 Months	2 ± 0	1.5 ± 0.51	0.5	0.00*
3 Months	2.3 ± 0.46	2 ± 0	0.3	0.02*

*Significant $p < 0.05$, Unpaired t-Test

TABLE 4
INTRAGROUP COMPARISON OF PAPILLARY INDEX SCORES (PIS)

Groups	Baseline		10 Days		1 Month		3 Month		F	p-value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Group A	1.06	0.24	1.39	0.50	2	0	2.3	0.46	48.21	<0.00001**
Group B	1.06	0.24	1.06	0.24	1.5	0.51	2	0	48.65	<0.00001**

** $p < 0.001$ (Highly Significant), One-way ANOVA repeated measures test

The Tables 3 & Table 4 show the Intergroup comparison of PIS showed a statistically significant difference between Group A and Group B from baseline to 3 months, while intragroup comparison demonstrated a highly significant improvement in both groups.

TABLE 5:
INTERGROUP COMPARISON OF BLACK TRIANGLE WIDTH (BTW)

Time Interval	Group A (in mm)	Group B (in mm)	Mean Difference	p-value
Baseline	0.99 ± 0.24	1.16 ± 0.35	-0.17	0.10
10 Days	0.82 ± 0.28	0.98 ± 0.26	-0.16	0.08
1 Months	0.48 ± 0.25	0.67 ± 0.25	-0.19	0.03*
3 Months	0.4 ± 0.18	0.47 ± 0.21	-0.07	0.09

*Significant $p < 0.05$, Unpaired t-Test

TABLE 6
INTRAGROUP COMPARISON OF BLACK TRIANGLE WIDTH (BTW)

Groups	Baseline		10 Days		1 Month		3 Month		F	p-value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Group A	0.99	0.24	0.82	0.28	0.48	0.25	0.4	0.18	86.63	<0.00001**
Group B	1.16	0.35	0.98	0.26	0.67	0.25	0.47	0.21	152.59	<0.00001**

** $p < 0.001$ (Highly Significant), One-way ANOVA repeated measures test

The Tables 5 & Table 6 show the Intergroup comparison of BTW showed a statistically significant difference between Group A and Group B from baseline to 3 months, while intragroup comparison demonstrated a highly significant improvement in both groups.

TABLE 7
INTERGROUP COMPARISON OF BLACK TRIANGLE HEIGHT (BTH)

Time Interval	Group A (in mm)	Group B (in mm)	Mean Difference	p-value
Baseline	1.97 ± 0.43	1.76 ± 0.54	0.21	0.22
10 Days	1.51 ± 0.38	1.53 ± 0.37	-0.02	0.85
1 Months	0.93 ± 0.38	1.06 ± 0.35	-0.13	0.30
3 Months	0.6 ± 0.31	0.9 ± 0.32	-0.3	0.00*

*Significant $p < 0.05$, Unpaired t-Test

TABLE 8
INTRAGROUP COMPARISON OF BLACK TRIANGLE HEIGHT (BTH)

Groups	Baseline		10 Days		1 Month		3 Month		F	p-value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Group A	1.97	0.43	1.51	0.38	0.93	0.38	0.6	0.31	154.57	<0.00001**
Group B	1.76	0.54	1.53	0.37	1.06	0.35	0.90	0.32	60.82	<0.00001**

** $p < 0.001$ (Highly Significant), One-way ANOVA repeated measures test

The Table 7 & Table 8 show the Intergroup comparison of BTH showed a statistically significant difference between Group A and Group B from baseline to 3 months, while intragroup comparison demonstrated a highly significant improvement in both groups.

TABLE 9
INTERGROUP COMPARISON OF BLACK TRIANGLE AREA (BTA)

Time Interval	Group A (in mm ²)	Group B (in mm ²)	Mean Difference	p-value
Baseline	0.98 ± 0.41	1.07 ± 0.62	-0.09	0.60
10 Days	0.62 ± 0.33	0.77 ± 0.37	-0.15	0.20
1 Months	0.22 ± 0.14	0.38 ± 0.28	-0.16	0.04*
3 Months	0.1 ± 0.08	0.23 ± 0.19	-0.13	0.02*

*Significant p < 0.05, Unpaired t-Test

TABLE 10
INTRAGROUP COMPARISON OF BLACK TRIANGLE AREA (BTA)

Groups	Baseline		10 Days		1 Month		3 Month		F	p-value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Group A	0.98	0.41	0.62	0.33	0.22	0.14	0.1	0.08	86.69	<0.00001**
Group B	1.07	0.62	0.77	0.37	0.38	0.28	0.23	0.19	63.26	<0.00001**

**p < 0.001 (Highly Significant), One-way ANOVA repeated measures test

The Table 9 & Table 10 show the Intergroup comparison of BTA showed a statistically significant difference between Group A and Group B from baseline to 3 months, while intragroup comparison demonstrated a highly significant improvement in both groups.

TABLE 11
INTERGROUP COMPARISON OF PERCENTAGE FILL IN BLACK TRIANGLE AREA

Time Interval	Group A (in %)	Group B (in %)	Mean Difference (in %)	p-value
10 Days	35.2 ± 15.41	32.2 ± 9.66	3	0.49
1 Months	78.8 ± 9.9	65.9 ± 6	12.9	0.000001***
3 Months	88.4 ± 6.25	78.8 ± 7.6	9.6	0.000**

**p < 0.001 (Highly Significant), *Significant p < 0.05, Unpaired t-Test

TABLE 12
INTRAGROUP COMPARISON OF PERCENTAGE FILL IN BLACK TRIANGLE AREA

Groups	10 Days (in %)		1 Month (in %)		3 Month (in %)		F	p-value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Group A	35.2	15.41	78.8	9.9	88.4	6.25	131.3	<0.00001**
Group B	32.2	9.66	65.9	6	78.8	7.6	158.1	<0.00001**

**p < 0.001 (Highly Significant), One-way ANOVA repeated measures test

The Table 11 & Table 12 show the Intergroup comparison of percentage reduction in black triangle area showed a statistically significant difference between Group A and Group B from baseline to 3 months, while intragroup comparison demonstrated a highly significant improvement in both groups.

TABLE 13
INTERGROUP COMPARISON OF PERCENTAGE CHANGE IN BLACK TRIANGLE AT 3 MONTHS FROM BASELINE

PERCENTAGE	GROUP A	GROUP B
100 %	2	0
90-99 %	3	0
80-89 %	13	9
70-79 %	0	7
60-69 %	0	2

The Table 13 shows the percentage change in Black triangle at 3 months from baseline using statistical data included in the study.

IV. DISCUSSION

The form and volume of the interdental space are governed by tooth morphology, alveolar bone height, and the presence of the interdental papilla. Loss of papilla results in gingival black triangles, which are considered aesthetically unacceptable when exceeding 3 mm, as reported by Kokich. [8] Loss of interdental papilla presents significant aesthetic, functional, and phonetic concerns, making its reconstruction a major clinical challenge.

Patients aged 18–60 years with aesthetic concerns related to gingival black triangles were included, as this age group shows a higher prevalence of open embrasures. Only sites with Papillary Index Score (PIS) 1 or 2 (Jemt, 1997) [6], indicating partial papillary loss with the presence of a contact point, were selected for the study. Patients with systemic diseases, periodontitis, drug-induced gingival overgrowth, pregnancy, tobacco use, or those on anticoagulants were excluded to avoid factors that could impair healing, alter gingival architecture, or affect treatment outcomes. These conditions may influence tissue response, bleeding, and regenerative potential, thereby compromising the reliability of results.

In the present study, Group B required more i-PRF applications than Group A, with 55.6% sites receiving four applications, while 77.8% of Group A sites required only two applications. (Table 2). Similar findings were reported by Becker et al. (2010) [9], where among 14 sites, 6 implant sites required three applications, and 3 sites showed 100% improvement, including 2 sites with three applications.

In the present study, PIS in Group A improved from 1.06 ± 0.24 at baseline to 2.3 ± 0.46 at 3 months, while in Group B it improved from 1.06 ± 0.24 to 2 ± 0 , showing greater papillary fill in Group A with highly significant intragroup differences ($p < 0.00001$). (Table 3 & 4). These findings are in accordance with Ahila et al. (2018) [10] (baseline: 1; 3 months: 2.96; 6 months: 3) and Gupta et al. (2012) [11] (3 months: 2.5 ± 0.52 ; 6 months: 2.4 ± 0.69), but contrast with Bertl et al. (2017) [12], where no change in PIS (score 2) was observed.

In the present study, BTW in Group A reduced from 0.99 ± 0.24 at baseline to 0.4 ± 0.18 at 3 months, while in Group B it reduced from 1.16 ± 0.35 to 0.47 ± 0.21 , showing significant intergroup difference at 1 month and highly significant intragroup improvement ($p < 0.00001$) (Table 5 & 6). These findings are consistent with Lee et al. (2016) [13] (0.63 ± 0.19), Prajapati et al. (2025) [14] (Group A: 1.04 ± 0.34 to 0.41 ± 0.35 ; Group B: 1.11 ± 0.38 to 0.60 ± 0.43), and Raval et al. (2021) [15] (baseline: 3.28 ± 0.89 with significant reduction over time).

In the present study, BTH in Group A reduced from 1.97 ± 0.43 at baseline to 0.6 ± 0.31 at 3 months, while in Group B it reduced from 1.76 ± 0.54 to 0.9 ± 0.32 , showing significant improvement in both groups ($p < 0.00001$), with intergroup significance observed from 1 to 3 months (Table 7 & 8). These findings are consistent with Ahila et al. (2018) [10] (4.38 ± 0.36 to 0.36 ± 0.638) and Raval et al. (2021) [15] (baseline: 4.12 ± 0.83 with significant reduction), but contrast with Bertl et al. (2017) [12], who reported no significant changes (1.8–2.3 mm).

In the present study, BTA in Group A reduced from 0.98 ± 0.41 at baseline to 0.1 ± 0.08 at 3 months, while in Group B it reduced from 1.07 ± 0.62 to 0.23 ± 0.19 , showing significant improvement over time ($p < 0.00001$), with intergroup significance observed from 10 days onwards (Table 9 & 10). These findings are consistent with Lee et al. (2016) [13] (0.58 ± 0.38), but contrast with Bertl et al. (2017) [12], who reported no significant changes in BTA over time.

In the present study, percentage fill in Group A increased from 35.2 ± 15.41 at 10 days to 88.4 ± 6.25 at 3 months, while in Group B it increased from 32.2 ± 9.66 to 78.8 ± 7.6 , showing significant improvement ($p < 0.00001$) with better

outcomes in Group A. At 3 months, Group A showed 2 sites with 100% fill and majority (13 sites) with 80–89% fill, whereas Group B showed no 100% fill (**Table 11,12 & 13**). These findings are consistent with **Nikhila Chandramohan et al. (2021)** [16] (41% enhancement at 3 months), **Raval et al. (2021)** [15] (65% to 85% fill), and **Becker et al. (2010)** [9], where multiple sites achieved up to 100% improvement.

V. CONCLUSION

Within the limitations of the present study, injectable platelet-rich fibrin (i-PRF) demonstrated significant efficacy in the reconstruction of deficient interdental and peri-implant papillae. Both groups showed statistically significant improvement in all clinical parameters (PIS, BTH, BTW, BTA, and percentage fill); however, better outcomes were observed in the interdental papilla (Group A) compared to the peri-implant papilla (Group B), which required more applications. Thus, i-PRF can be considered a promising, minimally invasive, and effective treatment modality for the management of gingival black triangles.

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